

SUBSTITUTION IN 5-*n*-PENTADECYLRESORCINOL

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5-*n*-Pentadecylresorcinol undergoes condensation with ethyl acetoacetate and malic acid to yield 5-hydroxycoumarin derivatives. On carboxylation, the Gattermann formylation and the Friedel-Crafts acetylation, the substitution also takes place in 2-position.

Substitution in a few 5-substituted resorcinols, such as orcinol, 2-resorcylic acid and 5-methoxyresorcinol, has been studied by various workers, and either 2- or 4-substituted derivatives or mixtures of both have been obtained (Weselsky, *Ber.* 1874, 7, 439; Gattermann and Kobner, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 279; Robertson and Robinson *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2196; Collie and Chrystall, *ibid.*, 1907, 91, 1804; Meyer, *Monatsh.*, 1887, 8, 430; Mody and Shah, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1952, 34A, 77; Grove *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1956). It was thought of interest to extend this study to a resorcinol derivative, such as 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol (I: R=H), with a long alkyl chain in 5-position.

The compound (I: R=H) on condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of either sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide afforded a product in good yield which furnished a yellow sodium salt with alkali without any fluorescence and which did not yield any styrene derivative with benzaldehyde. It has been assigned the 5-hydroxy-4-methyl-7-*n*-pentadecylcoumarin structure (II).

On carboxylation (I: R=H) furnished a monocarboxylic acid which on the Pechmann condensation with ethyl acetoacetate afforded a product which did not yield a styrene derivative. On decarboxylation it gave rise to a product which showed blue fluorescence with sulphuric acid. It was different from the 5-hydroxy-4-methyl-7-*n*-pentadecylcoumarin, described above. It has therefore been assigned the 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-*n*-pentadecylcoumarin (III: R=H) structure. The acid is therefore 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-*n*-pentadecylcoumarin-8-carboxylic acid (III: R=COOH) and the phenolic acid is 2:6-dihydroxy-4-*n*-pentadecylbenzoic acid (I: R=COOH).

The compound (I: R=H) on the Gattermann reaction furnished a formyl derivative which on methylation and oxidation with alkaline permanganate yielded an acid, identical with 2:6-dimethoxy-4-*n*-pentadecylbenzoic acid. The formyl derivative on the Knoevenagel condensation with ethyl acetoacetate furnished a coumarin which produced a yellow sodium salt with sodium hydroxide, indicating that it was a 5-hydroxycoumarin derivative. The formyl derivative has therefore been assigned the 2:6-dihydroxy-4-*n*-pentadecylbenzaldehyde structure (I: R=CHO). On the Perkin acetylation this aldehyde afforded a product which did not exhibit any fluorescence with concentrated sulphuric acid and developed a yellow colour with sodium hydroxide solution. It was found to be identical with the compound obtained on the Pechmann condensation of (I: R=H) with malic acid. It is therefore assigned the 5-hydroxy 7-*n*-pentadecylcoumarin structure.

The compound (I: R=H) on the Friedel-Crafts acetylation with acetyl chloride (1 mol.) furnished a ketone which, on methylation and oxidation with alkaline permanganate, afforded 2:6-dimethoxy-4-*n*-pentadecylbenzoic acid. Hence, the ketone is 2:6-dihydroxy-4-*n*-pentadecylacetophenone (I: R=COCH₃). On further reaction with acetic anhydride, as also on the Fries migration of 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol diacetate, a diacetyl derivative was obtained. This must be 2:4-diacetyl-5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol.

*E X P E R I M E N T A L

5-Hydroxy-4-methyl-7-n-pentadecylcoumarin.—A mixture of 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol (2 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (2 g.) and H₂SO₄ (conc., 8 c.c.) was left overnight. The product, obtained on pouring it in ice, was crystallised from rectified spirit in yellowish needles (1.3 g.), m.p. 142-43°. It dissolved in H₂SO₄ (conc.) with a yellow colour without any fluorescence and afforded sodium salt in NaOH solution. (Found: C, 78.3; H, 10.2. C₂₈H₄₈O₃ requires C, 77.7; H, 9.9%).

The same product was obtained when a mixture of 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol (1 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (1 g.) and P₂O₅ (4 g.) was kept for 3 hours and then poured on ice.

The *acetyl derivative* was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 89-91°. (Found: C, 75.2; H, 9.1. C₂₇H₄₆O₄ requires C, 75.7; H, 9.4%).

The *methyl ether* was prepared by refluxing the acetone solution of the substance with dimethyl sulphate in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate. It was crystallised from rectified spirit in colorless needles, m.p. 85-86°. (Found: C, 77.5; H, 9.6. C₂₈H₄₈O₃ requires C, 78.0; H, 10.1%).

2:6-Dihydroxy-4-n-pentadecylbenzoic Acid.—5-*n*-Pentadecylresorcinol (10 g.) was thoroughly mixed with potassium bicarbonate (20 g.) and anhydrous glycerine (20 g.), and the reaction mixture was heated in an oil-bath in a current of carbon dioxide at 115-20° for 5 hours. On cooling, water was added and the reaction mixture was acidified with HCl. The product obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining needles (6 g.), m.p. 136-38°. It developed a blue coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 72.84; H, 9.29. C₂₂H₃₈O₄ requires C, 72.49; H, 9.96%).

Methyl 2:6-Dimethoxy-4-n-pentadecylbenzoate.—The above acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed in acetone solution with dimethyl sulphate (1 g.) and potassium carbonate

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

(1.5 g.) for 15 hours. The product obtained was crystallised from alcohol in shining needles, m.p. 42-43°. (Found: C, 73.24; H, 10.20. $C_{25}H_{44}O_4$ requires C, 73.85; H, 10.41%.)

2:6-Dimethoxy-4-*n*-pentadecylbenzoic Acid.—The above ester was hydrolysed by refluxing with alcoholic potash (10%). The acid obtained was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 88-89°. It did not show any coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 74.14; H, 10.27. $C_{24}H_{40}O_4$ requires C, 73.57; H, 10.27%.)

7-Hydroxy-5-*n*-pentadecyl-4-methylcoumarin-8-carboxylic Acid.—A mixture of 2:6-dihydroxy-4-*n*-pentadecylbenzoic acid (1 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (1 g.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 4 c.c.) was kept overnight and then heated for 4 hours at 60-70°. The product, obtained on pouring it on crushed ice, was crystallised from alcohol in shining needles, m.p. 180°. It dissolved in H_2SO_4 (conc.) and alkali without any colour. (Found: C, 72.36; H, 8.35. $C_{28}H_{48}O_6$ requires C, 72.52; H, 8.90%.)

7-Hydroxy-5-*n*-pentadecyl-4-methylcoumarin.—The above acid was decarboxylated by heating with quinoline and copper powder at 180° for 15 minutes. The product, obtained on pouring the reaction mixture into excess of HCl (dil.), was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 127-28°. It developed a blue fluorescence with H_2SO_4 (conc.). (Found: C, 77.10; H, 9.70. $C_{25}H_{40}O_3$ requires C, 77.67; H, 9.91%.)

2:6-Dihydroxy-4-*n*-pentadecylbenzaldehyde.—Dry hydrogen chloride was passed through an externally cooled mixture of 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol (10 g.) and zinc cyanide (20 g.) in dry ether (100 c.c.) for 5 hours. The reaction mixture was kept overnight. Ether was then removed and the pasty mass obtained was boiled with water for about an hour. The product separating was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles (4 g.), m.p. 95-96°. It showed a deep red coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 75.92; H, 10.61. $C_{22}H_{36}O_3$ requires C, 75.81; H, 10.41%.)

The dimethyl ether, prepared as before, crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 66°. (Found: C, 76.28; H, 10.59. $C_{24}H_{40}O_3$ requires C, 76.55; H, 10.71%.)

The dimethyl ether (0.2 g.), suspended in water, was refluxed for 2 hours with a solution of potassium carbonate (0.5 g.) and potassium permanganate (0.5 g. in 15 c.c. of water). The product obtained on acidification was crystallised first from petroleum ether and then from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 88-89°. Mixed m.p. with 2:6-dimethoxy-4-*n*-pentadecylbenzoic acid, described before, was not depressed.

5-Hydroxy-7-*n*-pentadecyl-3-acetylcoumarin.—To a cooled mixture of 2:6-dihydroxy-4-*n*-pentadecylbenzaldehyde (0.5 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.7 g.) a few drops of piperidine were added. After keeping the reaction mixture overnight, HCl (dil.) was added. The product obtained was crystallised from rectified spirit in yellowish needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 150-52°. It did not exhibit any fluorescence with H_2SO_4 (conc.). With alkali it formed a yellow solution without any fluorescence. It did not develop any colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 75.45; H, 8.70. $C_{26}H_{46}O_4$ requires C, 75.32; H, 9.24%.)

5-Hydroxy-7-*n*-pentadecylcoumarin.—A mixture of 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol (3.2 g.), malic acid (1.33 g.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 6.4 c.c.) was heated at 70-80° for

3 hours. The product, obtained on pouring it in ice, was crystallised from rectified spirit in shining needles, m.p. 125-27°. It developed a yellow colour with alkali. (Found: C, 77.25; H, 9.57. $C_{21}H_{36}O_2$ requires C, 77.37; H, 9.74%).

The same coumarin was obtained when 2:6-dihydroxy-4-*n*-pentadecylbenzaldehyde (0.5 g.), sodium acetate (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) were refluxed in an oil-bath at 180° for 8 hours and the reaction mixture worked up as usual.

2:6-Dihydroxy-4-n-pentadecylacetophenone.—To 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol (16 g., 0.05M) in nitrobenzene (60 c.c.) anhydrous aluminium chloride (13.3 g., 0.1M) in nitrobenzene (20 c.c.) was added, followed by acetyl chloride (3.95 g., 0.05M). The reaction mixture was kept for 45 hours at room temperature. The product, obtained on decomposition with cold HCl and removal of nitrobenzene, was crystallised from acetic acid in needles (4 g.), m.p. 74-76°. It developed a red coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 75.63; H, 10.75. $C_{23}H_{38}O_2$ requires C, 76.19; H, 10.57%).

The *dimethyl ether* was prepared as before, b.p. 260°/10 mm. (Found: C, 77.42; H, 10.93. $C_{22}H_{42}O_2$ requires C, 76.91; H, 10.76%). On oxidation as before, it afforded 2:6-dimethoxy-4-*n*-pentadecylbenzoic acid, described above.

2:4-Diacetyl-5-n-pentadecylresorcinol.—5-*n*-Pentadecylresorcinol (8 g., 0.025M) and acetic anhydride (5.1 g., 0.05M) in nitrobenzene (20 c.c.) were treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (10 g., 0.075M) in nitrobenzene. The reaction mixture was kept overnight and worked up as usual. The product obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in shining needles (1.5 g.), m.p. 60-62°. It showed a red coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 73.99; H, 9.71. $C_{25}H_{40}O_4$ requires C, 74.25; H, 9.90%).

The same product was obtained when 2:6-dihydroxy-4-*n*-pentadecylacetophenone (2 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (1.5 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (3.5 g.) in nitrobenzene (50 c.c.) on a steam-bath for 6 hours and also when 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol diacetate (Kawamura, *J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1928, 3, 103) (2 g.) in nitrobenzene was kept with anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.33 g.) for 20 hours at room temperature and the reaction mixture worked up as usual.

Thanks of the authors are due to the Irvington Division of the Minnesota Mining and Manufacturing Co., New York, for the gift of 5-*n*-pentadecylresorcinol. One of them (S.P.) thanks the M.S. University of Baroda for the award of a research assistantship.